

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF MULTI-ADDITIVE WASTE MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE SOIL STABILIZATION

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Abstract

Problematic clay soils commonly found in tropical environments are frequently characterized by excessive plasticity, low shear strength, and inadequate bearing capacity, which restrict their direct use in pavement and foundation construction. This study investigates the effectiveness of a hybrid stabilization approach using MHA, QD, and BG as sustainable alternatives to conventional stabilizers. Laboratory evaluations comprising Atterberg limits, compaction characteristics, unconfined compressive strength (UCS), California bearing ratio (CBR), and microstructural assessment using scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM/EDX) were performed. MHA enhanced soil performance through pozzolanic reactions and cementitious bonding, QD improved packing density and particle interlock, and while BG contributed to load transfer and shear resistance by forming a granular skeleton. The combined application of 5% MHA, 15% QD, and 25% BG produced a marked synergistic effect, increasing UCS from 289 to 1459 kPa and CBR from 4.2% to 13.2%. Microstructural observations confirmed a dense matrix with reduced pore spaces and improved interparticle bonding. The findings demonstrate that multi-additive stabilization using agro-industrial waste materials provides a technically effective and environmentally sustainable solution for improving weak clay subgrades.

1. Introduction

Clay soils occurring in tropical and sub-tropical regions are widely recognized for their poor engineering behaviour, particularly their low shear strength, high plasticity, and pronounced volume change when subjected to moisture fluctuations. These characteristics often render such soils unsuitable for direct use as pavement subgrades or foundation materials without improvement (Khoshghalb et al., 2020; Nnochiri & Ogundipe, 2019).

Road failures linked to weak clay subgrades remain a persistent challenge in Nigeria and similar developing countries. Leading to high maintenance costs and reduced service life of infrastructure (Akinwumi et al., 2020). Conventional soil stabilization techniques typically involve the use of cement or lime both of which have proven effective in improving soil strength and durability. However, the increasing cost of these binders and growing concerns over their environmental impact, particularly carbon dioxide emissions associated with cement production, have necessitated the search for more sustainable alternatives (Basha et al., 2020; Tiwari & Satyam, 2021). As a result, attention has shifted towards the use of locally available, cost-effective and environmentally eco-friendly agro-industrial and construction waste materials.

Millet husk ash is an agricultural by-product rich in amorphous silica and alumina, which can participate in pozzolanic reactions in the presence of calcium, leading to the formation of cementitious compounds that enhance soil cohesion and strength (Ayele & Ahmed, 2021). Quarry dust generated during rock crushing operations has been shown to improve soil performance primarily through mechanical means by filling voids and improving particle packing and interlock (Kumar & Singh, 2018). Bush gravel, a lateritic coarse material commonly found in tropical regions, contributes to soil improvement by forming a load-bearing skeleton that enhances shear resistance and distributes applied stresses more effectively (Alhassan & Mohammed, 2022).

Although several studies have examined the individual application of agricultural ashes, quarry dust, or granular materials in soil stabilization, limited research has focused on the combined or hybrid use of these materials in clay soils. Hybrid stabilization is expected to harness both chemical and mechanical improvement mechanisms, resulting in superior performance compared with single-additive treatments. Therefore, this study evaluates the engineering and microstructural performance of clay soil stabilized with millet husk ash, quarry dust, and bush gravel used individually and in combination.

2. Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of multi-additive waste materials for the sustainable stabilization of clay soil intended for pavement subgrade applications. The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. Assess the influence of MHA on the strength and bearing characteristics of clay soil;
2. Examine the effect of quarry dust on soil compaction, strength, and load-bearing capacity
3. The contribution of bush gravel to the mechanical reinforcement of clay soil was evaluated
4. The combined (hybrid) effect of millet husk ash, quarry dust, and bush gravel on the engineering and microstructural properties of the stabilized soil was investigated.

3. Literature Review

Agricultural waste ashes, such as rice husk ash, corn cob ash, and millet husk ash, have been widely studied for soil stabilization owing to their pozzolanic potential. Akinwumi et al., (2020) reported that agro-waste ashes significantly reduce plasticity and improve strengths characteristics of clay soils through the formation of cementitious compounds. Similarly, Ayele and Ahmed (2021) observed that ashes rich in reactive silica enhance unconfined compressive strength when used at optimum contents, beyond which strength reduction may occur due to insufficient calcium for complete reactions.

Quarry dust has gained attention as a sustainable stabilizing material owing to its fine particle size and availability as a construction by-product. According to Kumar and Singh (2018) quarry dust improves soil gradation, leading to increased density and strength through better particle packing. Tiwari and Satyam (2021) further noted that quarry dust-treated clays exhibit improved CBR values, making them suitable for pavement subgrades, especially when combined with other stabilizing agents.

Granular materials, such as lateritic gravel and bush gravel, are commonly used to provide mechanical reinforcement to weak soil reinforcement. Alhassan and Mohammed (2022) reported that the inclusion of lateritic aggregates inclusion enhances shear strength and load distribution by forming a stable granular skeleton within fine-grained soils. This mechanism limits deformation and improves resistance to applied loads, particularly under repeated traffic loading conditions.

Recent studies have emphasized the benefits of combining chemical and mechanical stabilizers to achieve superior soil performance. Basha et al. (2020) highlighted that hybrid stabilization systems involving pozzolanic materials and granular fillers produce soil matrices with enhanced durability. Khoshghalb et al. (2020) also confirmed through microstructural analysis that hybrid-treated soils exhibit reduced pore spaces and improved interparticle bonding, resulting in significant gains in strength and stiffness.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1 Soil sampling and preparation

The clay soil used in this investigation was obtained from a depth of approximately 1.2 m below the natural ground surface to eliminate the influence of organic matter and topsoil contaminants. The disturbed soil samples were carefully excavated, sealed in polyethylene bags, and transported to the laboratory. Before testing, the soil was air-dried at room temperature, gently pulverized using a wooden mallet to prevent alteration of particle structure, and passed through a 2.0-mm British Standard sieve. This preparation ensured the uniformity of samples and compliance with standard laboratory testing procedures.

4.2 Stabilizing Materials

MHA was produced through a controlled combustion of dried millet husks in a muffle furnace at temperatures ranging between 550 °C and 650 °C. This temperature range was selected to maximize amorphous silica formation while preventing crystallization, which would reduce pozzolanic reactivity. After combustion, the ash was allowed to cool naturally, ground, and sieved through a 75- μ m sieve to improve its reactivity and uniform dispersion within the soil matrix. The pozzolanic reaction governing the stabilization process may be generally expressed as follows:

where C-S-H represents calcium silicate hydrate, which is the primary compound responsible for strength development. QD, a by-product of crushed rock aggregates, was collected from a local quarry. It was washed thoroughly to remove clayey impurities and oven-dried at 105 ± 5 °C. BG, a lateritic granular material, was washed and dried to remove deleterious substances. Both QD and BG function primarily as mechanical stabilizers by improving soil gradation, particle interlock, and load transfer mechanisms.

4.3 Mix Proportioning

Six soil mixtures were prepared on a dry weight basis to evaluate the individual and combined effects of the stabilizers. Millet husk ash was added at 5% and 10% of the dry soil weight, quarry dust at 15% and 20%, and bush gravel at 25%. A hybrid mixture of 5% MHA, 15% QD, and 25% BG were also prepared. Each mixture was thoroughly blended in dry condition to ensure homogeneity before the adding water at predetermined moisture contents required for compaction and strength testing.

4.4 Atterberg limit testing

The liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), and plasticity index (PI) of the untreated and treated soils were determined in accordance with ASTM D4318. The plasticity index was computed using the following relationship:

$$PI = LL - PL \quad (2)$$

These tests were conducted to evaluate changes in soil consistency, workability, and plasticity characteristics resulting from the addition of the stabilizing materials.

4.5 Compaction characteristics

Standard Proctor compaction tests were conducted to determine the optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) of each soil mixture in accordance with ASTM D698. Compaction was achieved using a standard rammer and mould. The dry density (ρ_d) was calculated from the bulk density (ρ) and moisture content (w) using the following equation:

$$\rho_d = \frac{\rho}{1 + w} \quad (3)$$

Where w is expressed as a decimal point. The compaction characteristics were used to prepare specimens for subsequent strength tests at the respective OMCs.

4.6 Unconfined compressive strength test

The unconfined compressive strength (UCS) test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D2166 to evaluate the shear strength of the untreated and stabilized soil samples. Cylindrical specimens with a height-to-diameter ratio of approximately 2:1 were prepared by compacting the soil at OMC and MDD in cylindrical molds. The specimens were carefully extruded and cured 7 days in sealed polythene bags at room temperature to prevent moisture loss and allow pozzolanic reactions to occur. The UCS was determined by applying an axial load at a constant strain rate until failure. The unconfined compressive strength was calculated as follows:

$$UCS = \frac{P}{A} \quad (4)$$

Where P is the maximum axial load at failure (N) and A is the corrected cross-sectional area of the specimen (mm^2). The UCS test provides a direct measure of the strength improvement achieved through stabilization.

4.7 California bearing ratio test

The California bearing ratio (CBR) test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D1883 to assess the bearing capacity of the untreated and treated soils for pavement subgrade applications. The Samples were compacted at their respective OMCs and group with MDD in standard CBR molds. The specimens were soaked for 96 hours before testing to simulate the worst-case field moisture conditions.

The CBR value was computed using the following expression:

$$CBR(\%) = \frac{P_{test}}{P_{standard}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where P_{test} is the measured load corresponding to a given penetration and $P_{standard}$ is the standard load at the same penetration. The CBR results were used to evaluate the suitability of the stabilised soils for pavement construction.

4.8 Microstructural analysis (SEM/EDX)

Microstructural analysis was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) to examine changes in soil fabric, pore structure, and elemental composition resulting from stabilization at NIBRRI (Abuja, Nigeria). Selected specimens were oven-dried, mounted on aluminum stubs, and coated with a thin layer of gold to enhance the conductivity of the samples. SEM imaging was used to observe particle morphology, interparticle bonding, and pore distribution, while EDX

analysis provided qualitative information on elemental composition and the presence of silica-rich cementitious products associated with pozzolanic reactions.

4.9 Data analysis

All laboratory tests were conducted in duplicates to ensure the consistency and reliability of the results, and the average values were reported. The results of the various tests were analyzed and compared to assess the individual and combined effects of MHA, QD, and BG on the engineering performance of the clay soil.

5. Results and Analysis

This section presents and discusses the results of laboratory testing of untreated and stabilized clay soil. The effects of MHA, QD) and BG index properties, compaction characteristics, strength, bearing capacity, and microstructure are evaluated.

5.1. Index properties of the untreated soil

As shown in Table 1, the untreated clay soil exhibited high plasticity, which is typical of tropical clay soils with poor engineering performance. The high plasticity index indicates susceptibility to excessive deformation, shrink–swell behavior, and strength loss under varying moisture conditions, making the soil unsuitable for direct use as pavement subgrade material.

Table 1: Index Properties of the untreated Clay Soil

Property (%)	Value	Soil Classification
Liquid limit (LL)	52	(USCS) CH
Plastic limit (PL)	26	„
Plasticity Index (PI)	26	„

The soil exhibits a liquid limit of 52% and a plastic limit of 26%, resulting in a plasticity index of 26%. According to USCS, the soil is classified as high plastic clay (CH). This classification indicates a soil with high compressibility, low shear strength in its natural state, and significant shrink–swell potential, is unsuitable for direct use as a pavement subgrade or foundation material without stabilization. Such soils are highly sensitive to moisture variation and are prone to strength loss under soaked conditions, which justifies the need for stabilization before engineering application.

5.2. Stabilization effect on Atterberg limits

The incorporation of stabilizing materials resulted in a progressive reduction in the clay soil's plasticity characteristics of the clay soil (Table 2).

Table 2: Atterberg Limits of untreated and treated soils

Mix ID	LL (%)	PL (%)	PI (%)
Untreated	52	26	26
5% MHA	45	25	20
10% MHA	43	24	19
15% QD	41	26	15
20% QD	39	27	12
25% BG	44	28	16
Hybrid (MHA+QD+BG)	36	29	7

The untreated clay soil recorded a plasticity index (PI) of 26%, classifying it as a high-plasticity clay (CH) according to the ASM D2487. Such soils are generally considered unsuitable for pavement subgrades without treatment because of their high shrink–swell potential.

Figure 1. Variation of the Atterberg limits with the stabilization

As shown in Figure 1, upon stabilization, the plasticity index reduced progressively, with the hybrid mixture (5% MHA + 15% QD + 25% BG) achieving a PI of approximately 7%. This value falls within the range typically considered acceptable for road construction subgrade materials, as recommended by several highway agencies, including the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Works and international practice guidelines (AASHTO M145). The plasticity reduction indicates improved soil workability and reduced moisture sensitivity, which is consistent with the findings of Akinwumi et al. (2020) and Ayele and Ahmed (2021).

5.3. Compaction Characteristics

Table 3 shows the compaction characteristics of the untreated and stabilized soil mixtures. The results indicate that the inclusion of millet husk ash, quarry dust, and bush gravel significantly influenced the soils optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD).

Table 3: Compaction characteristics of untreated and treated soils

Mix ID	OMC (%)	MDD (Mg/m ³)
Untreated	18.5	1.62
5% MHA	19.8	1.59
10% MHA	20.3	1.57
15% QD	17.2	1.68
20% QD	16.6	1.71
25% BG	16.9	1.66
Hybrid (MHA+QD+BG)	17.0	1.74

The addition of MHA resulted in a slight increase (Figure 2) in optimum moisture content due to its porous structure and higher water absorption capacity, while the maximum dry density decreased marginally.

Figure 2. Variation in the compaction characteristics with stabilization

The addition of MHA increased the optimum moisture content to 19.8% and 20.3% at 5% and 10% MHA, respectively, due to the porous nature and higher water absorption of the ash. A slight reduction in the maximum dry density was also observed. In contrast, quarry dust and bush gravel reduced the optimum moisture content and increased the maximum dry density by improving particle packing. The hybrid mixture achieved the highest maximum dry density of 1.74 Mg/m³, indicating improved densification and load-bearing capacity. According to ASTM D698, such increases in dry density indicates improved structural performance of subgrade materials.

5.4. Unconfined compressive strength (UCS)

The untreated clay soil exhibited low UCS (Table 3), confirming its weak shear strength.

Table 3: Unconfined compressive strength results

Mix ID	UCS (Kpa)
Untreated	289
5% MHA	412
10% MHA	401
15% QD	598
20% QD	623
25% BG	374
Hybrid (MHA+QD+BG)	1459

The untreated clay soil recorded a low UCS of 289 kPa, confirming its weak shear strength and unsuitability for use as a pavement subgrade in its natural state. Stabilization led to substantial strength improvement, with the hybrid mixture achieving a UCS of 1459 kPa. Stabilized subgrade soils with UCS values in excess of approximately 800–1000 kPa are generally considered adequate for low- to medium-traffic pavement applications, as such values reflect sufficient stiffness and resistance to deformation under loading (Basha et al., 2020; Tiwari & Satyam, 2021).

Figure 3. Variation of the unconfined compressive strength with stabilization

Therefore, the UCS obtained (Figure 3) for the hybrid-stabilized soil exceeds commonly reported performance thresholds, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining chemical stabilization from millet husk ash with mechanical reinforcement provided by quarry dust and bush gravel. Recent experimental studies on treated clay soils have reported similar strength enhancement resulting from hybrid stabilization approaches (Khoshghalb et al., 2020; Akinwumi et al., 2020).

5.5 California Bearing Ratio (CBR)

The CBR value of the untreated soil was very low (Table 4), indicating poor load-bearing capacity. All stabilization methods improved CBR values, with quarry dust showing better improvement than MHA and bush gravel when used individually. The hybrid-stabilized soil exhibited the highest CBR value, exceeding the minimum requirements for pavement subgrade applications.

Table 4: Results of California Bearing Ratio

Mix ID	CBR (%)
Untreated	4.2
5% MHA	5.6
10% MHA	5.3
15% QD	7.2
20% QD	7.8
25% BG	6.2
Hybrid (MHA+QD+BG)	13.2

The soaked CBR value for the untreated soil was 4.2%, which is below the minimum requirement for pavement subgrades in most design manuals. For instance, the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Works and AASHTO guidelines typically recommend minimum soaked CBR values of 5%–10% for subgrade materials, depending on traffic class.

Stabilization improved the CBR (Figure 4) values across all mixes, with the hybrid mixture achieving a CBR of 13.2%. This value exceeds the minimum requirement for subgrade materials and approaches the recommended for selected subgrade or subbase layers in low-volume roads. This improvement confirms the suitability of the hybrid-stabilized soil for pavement applications, which is consistent with the results reported by Alhassan and Mohammed (2022) and Tiwari and Satyam (2021).

Figure 4. Variation of California Bearing Ratio with Stabilization

5.6 Microstructural analysis (SEM/EDX)

The SEM images of the untreated soil (Figure 5) revealed a dispersed clay fabric with numerous micropores, explaining its low strength. MHA-treated samples showed cementitious gels bridging soil particles, while QD-treated samples exhibited reduced void spaces and improved packing density. Bush gravel samples displayed a skeletal structure that enhanced stress transfer.

Figure 5. SEM image of the untreated soil

The SEM analysis of the untreated soil revealed a dispersed clay fabric with significant microporosity, explaining its poor strength and bearing capacity. In contrast, the hybrid-stabilized soil exhibited a dense and compact structure with reduced pore spaces and strong interparticle bonding. The hybrid-stabilized soil (Figure 6) exhibited a dense, compact microstructure with strong interparticle bonding. EDX analysis confirmed the presence of increased silica and calcium peaks, validating the formation of calcium silicate hydrate compounds responsible for strength enhancement.

Figure 6. SEM Image of the hybrid-stabilized soil

The EDX spectra showed increased silica and calcium content in the stabilized samples, confirming the formation of (C–S–H compounds). This microstructural evidence supports the observed improvements in UCS and CBR and is consistent with the stabilization mechanisms reported by Akinwumi et al. (2020) and Khoshghalb et al. (2020).

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study evaluated the effectiveness of MHA, QD, and BG as sustainable stabilizing agents for problematic clay soil. The experimental results clearly demonstrate that each material contributes to soil improvement through distinct mechanisms. Millet husk ash enhanced soil strength through pozzolanic reactions, resulting in improved interparticle bonding and reduced plasticity. Quarry dust improves soil gradation and packing density, thereby increasing compaction efficiency and load-bearing capacity. Bush gravel provided mechanical reinforcement by forming a granular skeletal framework that enhanced shear resistance and stress distribution.

MHA, QD, and BG produced moderate improvements in unconfined compressive strength and California Bearing Ratio when applied individually. However, the combined application of 5% MHA, 15% QD, and 25% BG

resulted in a pronounced synergistic effect. The unconfined compressive strength increased from 289 kPa for the untreated soil to 1459 kPa, while the CBR increased from 4.2% to 13.2%. These values satisfy the minimum requirements for pavement subgrade materials in the construction of low- to medium-traffic road. Microstructural analysis using SEM/EDX confirmed the formation of a dense and well-interlocked soil matrix in the hybrid-stabilized samples. The presence of silica-rich cementitious gels, reduced pore spaces, and improved particle interlocking explain the significant enhancement in mechanical performance. Overall, multi-additive stabilization using agro-industrial and construction waste materials is a technically viable, environmentally sustainable, and cost-effective alternative to conventional cement or lime stabilization for weak clay soils.

Based on the Atterberg limits, UCS, and CBR results, the hybrid-stabilized soil meets or exceeds the commonly adopted requirements for pavement subgrade materials under ASTM, AASHTO, and Nigerian highway specifications. The results confirm that the combination of millet husk ash, quarry dust, and bush gravel provides a technically acceptable and sustainable alternative to conventional cement or lime stabilization.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

Hybrid stabilization using millet husk ash, quarry dust, and bush gravel is recommended to improve weak clay soils intended for pavement subgrade applications, particularly in tropical regions where such materials are readily available.

1. The optimal mix proportions identified in this study (5% millet husk ash, 15% quarry dust, and 25% bush gravel) should be adopted in practice to achieve a balanced combination of chemical bonding and mechanical reinforcement.
2. Field-scale trials should be conducted to validate the laboratory results and assess the long-term performance of the stabilized soil under actual traffic loading and environmental conditions. Durability studies involving repeated wetting–drying cycles and seasonal moisture variations are recommended.
3. To quantify the economic and sustainability benefits, Life-cycle cost and environmental impact assessments should be conducted.
4. Further research should explore the performance of other locally available agricultural and industrial by-products in hybrid stabilization systems and their suitability for higher traffic categories and foundation applications.

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